

A Case Study: FMG-based Gesture Recognition using High-Density Piezoelectric Electronic Skin and Machine Learning

Yahya Abbass¹, Silvana Miranda Montenegro², Fabio Egle², Moustafa Saleh^{1,3}, Maurizio Valle¹, and Claudio Castellini^{2,4}

¹Department of Electrical, Electronic, Telecommunications Engineering, and Naval Architecture (DITEN), University of Genoa, 16126 Genoa, Italy

²Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, 91052 Erlangen, Germany

³Department of Computer and Communication Engineering, Lebanese International University (LIU), Beirut 1000, Lebanon

⁴Institute of Robotics and Mechatronics, German Aerospace center (DLR), 82234 Wessling, Germany

Manuscript received 23 August 2025; revised 4 October 2025; accepted 14 October 2025. Date of publication 20 October 2025; date of current version 11 November 2025.

Abstract—During muscle contractions, force distributions are generated on muscle surfaces due to muscle activity, which is applicable for control in a human–machine interface. It has been proven that the force distribution from the corresponding body motions can be recorded utilizing the so-called Force Myography (FMG). Flexible piezoelectric sensors with attractive sensing properties have been widely used in several areas to detect force variations through wearable devices. In this letter, we developed an FMG armband composed of high-density (24 sensors) piezoelectric electronic skin and multichannel embedded electronics. The FMG armband was used to recognize eleven hand and wrist gestures performed by able-bodied subjects. To do this, two signal-processing approaches (front-end approach and feature-based approach) were developed to process the FMG patterns and extract the proper features. The processed FMG patterns were evaluated and identified by employing various classical machine learning algorithms, and an average gesture recognition accuracy of 98% for wrist gestures was obtained. This letter demonstrates the feasibility of using high-density piezoelectric skin for FMG and leads to alternative methods for gesture recognition in biomedical applications.

Index Terms—Sensor systems, force myography (FMG), gesture recognition, human–machine interfaces, piezoelectric sensors, wearable sensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Smart wearable technologies are rapidly revolutionizing users' experiences in various fields, such as human–machine interfaces (HMIs), robotic tactile sensing, personalized healthcare, and virtual/augmented reality [1]. For instance, wearable human gesture recognition systems for control of robotic systems are of particular interest due to the versatile commands the human hands can order. Recent advances in wearable electronics and materials research have allowed gesture recognition through indirect monitoring of forearm muscle activities. Prominent methodologies for this purpose include surface electromyography (sEMG) [2], electroencephalography [3], mechanomyography [4], and force myography (FMG) [5]. However, most HMI perform gesture recognition by measuring sEMG signals through noninvasive methods on the skin surface. It records the electrophysiological activities of muscle tissues, offering a direct reflection of the real-time neural and muscular status during movement. However, sEMG faces several unresolved challenges, such as low signal strength, susceptibility to muscle crosstalk, and significant system power consumption [6]. Contrasting with techniques that measure bioelectrical

activities, FMG is an alternative approach to detecting hand gestures [5].

Unlike sEMG, FMG detects muscle deformations associated with muscle activity. These forces are detectable by deploying pressure sensors or other devices capable of sensing muscle deformation. In most of the recent FMG studies, different sensing technologies, including Force-sensing resistors (FSRs) and piezoelectric sensors, have been used to measure muscle contraction [5]. These sensing technologies are commonly combined with machine learning (ML) techniques to better recognize the performed gesture. FSRs have been combined with classical ML techniques for gesture recognition [5] or intent detection in prosthetic hands [7]. Such sensors were used due to their simple structures and are low-cost devices, but their applicability is sometimes limited by their relatively low precision. For that reason, it is observed that FMG is still relatively little explored compared with other techniques, such as sEMG. Although piezoelectric tactile devices are not often used in robotic hand control, there are several reports on their use in HMIs [8] and gesture detection [9]. The flexibility and sensitivity of such sensors facilitate their application as wearable sensor patches. Dong et al. [10] used a single polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) piezoelectric sensor on the wrist to detect two hand gestures (hand open and hand closed). Similarly, Booth and Goldsmith [11] developed a wristband using six piezoelectric sensors to recognize hand and wrist gestures. Most of the aforementioned studies developed an FMG system that is based on a few number of piezoelectric sensors

Corresponding author: Yahya Abbass (e-mail: yahya.abbass@unige.it).
Yahya Abbass and Silvana Miranda Montenegro contributed equally to this work.
Associate Editor: Jesus M Corres.
Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/LENS.2025.3624027

Fig. 1. (a) Single sensor structure: a P(VDF-TrFE) layer sandwiched between two electrodes. (b) Structure of the FMG armband. The armband incorporates 24 PVDF sensors distributed equally over two sensing patches (SP) and EE. (c) Experimental setup for data collection using the FMG armband; the armband is placed on the forearm of the right hand.

(up to six sensors). Moreover, it has been concluded that the number and placement of the sensors significantly impact the accuracy of gesture recognition [12]. For example, a study of upper limb movements showed that increasing the spatial coverage location of FSR sensors significantly improves accuracy and that different combinations of FSR arm bands produced different results [13].

Consequently, this study investigates high-density piezoelectric electronic skin (e-skin) for gesture recognition to substitute conventional FMG techniques. Unlike previously developed FMG sensors, we developed high-density FMG armband hosting 24 piezoelectric sensors distributed over two e-skins. The armband was mounted on the forearm, combined with the classical ML algorithm, and evaluated in capturing 11 hand and wrist gestures. Moreover, this letter presents a comparison between two signal preprocessing approaches for gesture recognition, highlighting the power of the developed FMG technique. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first armband that is based on distributed piezoelectric sensors and capable of performing satisfactory gesture recognition.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Tactile Armband

We have designed a fully screen-printed flexible sensor array based on P(VDF-TrFE) poly(vinylidene fluoride trifluor-oethylene) piezoelectric polymer sensors, which were fabricated by JOANNEUM RESEARCH [14]. The manufacturing process utilizes screen printing technology to print P(VDF-TrFE) repeated sensors on flexible substrates. Fig. 1(a) shows the structure of a single P(VDF-TrFE) sensor. First, a bottom electrode is screen-printed on a transparent and flexible (175 μm thick) DIN A4 plastic foil (Melinex ST 725) substrate. Second, a ferroelectric polymer P(VDF-TrFE) layer (5.1 μm thick) is then screen-printed onto the bottom electrodes, followed by screen printing of the top electrodes (PEDOT: PSS). A ultraviolet (UV)-curable lacquer layer is then deposited on top for overall sensor protection. Experimental validation of the sensors proved the intrinsic flexibility of the e-skin [15]. The aforementioned process is used to fabricate two e-skins that each host 12 sensors. To use the e-skins, the integration process described in [15] is employed to protect the skin electrically and mechanically, while allowing it to conform. First,

the e-skin is connected to a routing printed circuit board (PCB), and hot glue is applied. Second, the e-skin is shielded using single-sided electrically conductive tapes (Model tesa 60234, tesa). Finally, the shielding layer is connected to the ground of the embedded electronics (EE) using a self-adhesive copper foil tape and a wire forming the sensing patch (SP).

The EE presented in [15] is employed in this study. It is composed of a BL600 module (Laird Connectivity, USA) and DDC232 (Texas Instrument, USA) current-input analog-to-digital converter. The design can handle up to 32 sensors through two sockets with 16 input channels each. The device architecture features a simultaneous sampling of the 32 input channels with a configurable sampling rate of up to 6 kHz. The BL600 contains an ultra-low-power microcontroller based on an ARM Cortex M0 chip that reads, processes, and transmits sensor data. In the present study, the EE is configured to collect and process tactile data from 24 sensors at 2 K samples/s. However, the transmission rate through the UART connection is measured to be 900 samples/s.

In this study, two SPs were attached to an elastic bandage using double-sided adhesive tape. The bandage had a soft elastic loop-side Velcro of 5.5 cm width and 30 cm length. It allowed variable tightness, as a plastic slot is sewn to one end of the band, which allows insertion of the other end to be pulled to the desired tightness and then closed using the hook-side velcro. Fig. 1(b) shows the two SPs attached to the interior of the elastic bandage, allowing direct contact with the skin. The EE is placed in a small shielded box and mounted onto the exterior of the elastic bandage forming the FMG armband shown in Fig. 1(b). All the materials used in the integration process (i.e., conductive and adhesive tapes, flat cables, and elastic bandage) are biocompatible.

B. Gesture Recognition

1) *Experimental Setup and Protocol*: Five right-handed healthy subjects (three males and two females), aged 23–30 years and with body mass index ≈ 21 (normal weight), participated in this study.

The FMG armband was placed on the upper half of the right forearm, as shown in Fig. 1(c). The armband is positioned so that one of the SPs targets the ventral side of the forearm while the second SP targets the dorsal side of the forearm. During the experiment, subjects were seated in front of a monitor, as shown in Fig. 1(c). The subjects were instructed to mimic a virtual hand shown by a graphical user interface (GUI) displayed on the monitor. The virtual hand was used as a ground truth for the gesture to be performed and for the later stages of the data processing. The virtual hand was programmed to show a sequence of 11 hand and wrist gestures, as shown in Fig. 2(a). For each step in the sequence, the virtual hand holds the gesture for 5 s and then returns to the rest (RT) position. The tactile signals from the 24 sensors (12 in each SP), along with the real-time hand position, are time-stamped and saved using a C#-based software suite. The stimulus sequence was repeated ten times, thus generating a dataset for each subject that is composed of ten trials per gesture. The dataset can be formulated as $\mathcal{D} = \{(X_i, y_i); X_i \in \mathbb{R}^{N_s \times N_c}, y_i \in \{11 \text{ gestures}\}, i = 1, \dots, 110\}$, where $N_c = 24$ is the number of sensors, $N_s = 4500$ is the number of samples (900 Samples/s \times 5 s), and $sb \in \{\text{five subjects}\}$. Fig. 2(b) shows an example of the response of the 24 sensors to the sequence of gestures performed by one subject.

2) *Recognition Approaches*: To conduct the offline analysis of gesture recognition, the dataset \mathcal{D}_{sb} is processed and used to develop preprocessing approaches for gesture recognition. Two classical approaches based on tactile signals and handcrafted features were developed to perform the gesture recognition.

1) *End-to-end approach (EEA)*: Following the work done in [8], the dataset \mathcal{D} was subjected to a dead-band with a constant

Fig. 2. (a) List of the targeted gestures. (b) Response of the 24 sensors within the FMG armband to the sequence of gestures performed by one subject.

dead band of $c_{db} = 10^{-4}$ to diminish the effect of unwanted variations. The signal is integrated by applying the cumulative sum, leading to piecewise constant segments with large offsets over time. To counteract this shift effect, a Butterworth high-pass filter (cutoff = 0.01 Hz, order = 3) is applied to the integrated signal.

- 2) Feature-based approach (FBA): In this approach, different time and frequency features were extracted and normalized from each $X_i \in \mathcal{D}_{sb}$. Specifically, the set of features is {Maximum (Max), Minimum (Min), Standard Deviation (SD), Mean Absolute Value (MAV), Slope Sign Change (SSC), Zero Crossing (ZC), Mean Frequency (MNF), Median Frequency (MDF), Peak Frequency (PF), and Mean Power (MNP)}. Consequently, each $X_i \in \mathcal{D}$ was transformed to $X_i^f \in \mathcal{D}^f$, where $\mathcal{D}^f = \{(X_i^f, y_i); X_i^f \in \mathbb{R}^{10 \times N_c}, y_i \in \{11 \text{ gestures}\}\}$.

For both approaches (EEA and FBA), two recognition scenarios were considered. The first scenario tackles the recognition of all 11 gestures (hand and wrist gestures), while the second considers only the wrist gestures, including *PG*, *WF*, *WE*, *WS*, and *WP*. For that reason, two subset datasets \mathcal{D}^w and \mathcal{D}^{fw} representing the wrist gestures in the EEA and FBA approaches were extracted from \mathcal{D} and \mathcal{D}^f , respectively, where $\mathcal{D}^w = \{(X_i, y_i); X_i \in \mathbb{R}^{900 \times N_c}, y_i \in \{\text{five wrist gestures}\}\}$ and $\mathcal{D}^{fw} = \{(X_i^f, y_i); X_i^f \in \mathbb{R}^{10 \times N_c}, y_i \in \{\text{five wrist gestures}\}\}$.

- 3) *Classification Algorithms*: In this study, some frequently applied ML algorithms have been selected, including random forest (RF), linear discriminant analysis (LDA), logistic regression (LR), support vector machine (SVM), and k-nearest neighbors (KNN). The algorithms were fitted and validated using a k -fold cross-validation technique with $k = 5$. In the FBA approach, $1/k$ of the dataset \mathcal{D}^f was kept aside to test the algorithms trained with the rest of the data. This procedure was repeated k times, and the mean and SD of the accuracy over the iterations are reported. As for the EEA approach, it is important to note that testing on potentially immediate neighbor data points (\mathcal{D}) may have similar effects to actually testing on the training set. For that reason, the k -fold cross-validation is conducted through the *leave-one-trial-out* technique.

Table 1. Classification performance of the ML algorithms using the EEA and FBA approaches for the full set of gestures (\mathcal{D} and \mathcal{D}^f) and wrist gestures (\mathcal{D}^w and \mathcal{D}^{fw})

Algorithm	Average \pm STD			
	Dataset			
	\mathcal{D} (EEA)	\mathcal{D}^f (FBA)	\mathcal{D}^w (EEA)	\mathcal{D}^{fw} (FBA)
KNN	64.2 \pm 9.4	82.1 \pm 5.8	75.2 \pm 5.6	96.0 \pm 4.8
LDA	74.5 \pm 7.8	84.9 \pm 7.4	88.4 \pm 6.2	96.4 \pm 1.6
LR	77.0 \pm 6.8	90.8\pm3.8	87.8 \pm 5.1	98.4\pm1.6
RF	74.6 \pm 5.7	88.5 \pm 4.2	83.0 \pm 2.8	93.6 \pm 2.1
SVM	72.3 \pm 4.9	86.5 \pm 6.0	80.8 \pm 1.7	95.2 \pm 1.7

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In a gesture recognition study, for the same motion, the force-distribution signals might differ because of muscle structure, muscle volume, and contraction strength. In addition, it is not possible to place the FMG armband exactly at the same position for all the subjects, which generally leads to subject-specific patterns. Moreover, during the experiments, subjects were asked to perform gestures with no constraints on motion speed. This, in turn, influenced the response of the armband as piezoelectric sensors are sensitive to the acceleration of motion. To recognize the gestures, two preprocessing approaches (EEA and FBA) were developed to process the tactile signals from the armband. Table 1 summarizes the classification performance of the ML algorithms when trained to recognize all gestures (\mathcal{D} and \mathcal{D}^f) or only wrist gestures (\mathcal{D}^w and \mathcal{D}^{fw}). It is noticed that the FBA approach outperformed the EEA approach in both recognition problems (all gestures and only wrist gestures). In particular, the LR algorithm achieved an average classification accuracy of 98.4% \pm 1.6% for wrist gestures using the features extracted from the FBA approach, which is higher than that achieved by the EEA approach (87.8% \pm 5.1%). LR also achieved the highest accuracy when considering all gestures. For instance, the average classification accuracy dropped to 90.8% \pm 3.8% using the FBA and to 77% \pm 6.8% using the EEA approach. The aforementioned results indicate that time and frequency features extracted within the FBA approach are sufficient, more than the raw signals to represent the gesture patterns, and that the LR algorithm is applicable for FMG-pattern recognition. This is aligned with previous studies on gesture recognition using FMG sensors [12]. Fig. 3 shows the confusion matrix obtained using the LR algorithm for all gestures. The LR algorithm was trained to recognize gestures with the \mathcal{D}_{sb}^f dataset (all gestures). For all the subjects, the LR algorithm was able to effectively recognize the gestures as illustrated by the clear dark diagonal in the confusion matrices.

Although the geometry of the SP within the armband is not uniform (matrix shape allowing better processing), it offers higher muscle coverage with respect to the literature [1]. Importantly, the sensing system is modular, and the geometries of the e-skin can be redesigned, allowing a better coverage of the full muscle activity either by integrating more sensors or developing muscle-selective design while maintaining the flexibility of the FMG armband as stated in [5]. In addition to muscle coverage, wearable devices may be unable to accommodate large batteries for power management, limiting their operation, usage, and functionality [1]. However, the power consumption of the interface electronics used in the FMG armband is 300 mW. When supplied with a single 2 Ah Lithium polymer battery with a voltage of 3.7 V, the battery lifetime expectancy is 22 h of working time, and this includes continuous sampling and processing of tactile signals. The system is

Fig. 3. Confusion matrices obtained using the LR algorithm. The LR algorithm was trained to recognize gestures within the D_{sb}^f dataset (all gestures).

therefore economical in terms of power consumption and can provide long-term usage (> 8 h, the duration of a working day). Therefore, in addition to the performed experiments, the power efficiency of the developed armband demonstrated that it is a feasible tool for FMG recording, which would provide an alternative approach for body motion registration during daily-life interactions.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, an e-skin integrating 24 piezoelectric sensors was used to develop an FMG armband for gesture recognition. Due to their flexibility, piezoelectric sensors are integrated into an elastic bandage. Therefore, the FMG acquisition device is completely flexible, which enhances the wearing comfort and frees the body's motions. The armband was combined with signal processing approaches and classical ML algorithms to recognize 11 hand gestures performed by healthy subjects. Results demonstrated the ability of the armband and the developed approaches to recognize the gestures with an accuracy of 90%. In addition to the achieved results, the special material properties of the piezoelectric sensors pave the way to design an advanced FMG acquisition device in the next step. The developed system can be improved by modifying the shape of the high-density e-skin for a more precise recording of FMG maps. The data recording position should be optimized with an associated physiological study of human muscle structures. Moreover, validation methods like cross-subject and leave-one-subject-out will be explored to check the performance of the developed approaches. In addition, more subjects should be recruited to implement an in-depth investigation of the proposed approach for body motion registration, especially for FMG-based prostheses that are desired for limb amputees.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported in part by the European Commission's Horizon Europe Framework Program through project IntelliMan (AI-Powered Manipulation System for Advanced Robotic Service, Manufacturing and Prosthetics) under Grant 101070136 and in part by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) under the Robotics Institute Germany (RIG). The authors would like to thank IIT Genova, Italy, and INAIL Centro Protesi, Italy, for making available their virtual model of the Hannes prosthetic arm.

This work involved human subjects or animals in its research. Approval of all ethical and experimental procedures and protocols was granted by the Region Liguria Ethical Committee under Application No. 172REG2016.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Tchanchane, H. Zhou, S. Zhang, and G. Alici, "A review of hand gesture recognition systems based on noninvasive wearable sensors," *Adv. Intell. Syst.*, vol. 5, no. 10, 2023, Art. no. 2300207.
- [2] K. Li, J. Zhang, L. Wang, M. Zhang, J. Li, and S. Bao, "A review of the key technologies for sEMG-based human-robot interaction systems," *Biomed. Signal Process. Control*, vol. 62, Sep. 2020, Art. no. 102074.
- [3] L. Schreiner, S. Sieghartsleitner, K. Mayr, H. Pretl, and C. Guger, "Hand gesture decoding using ultra-high-density EEG," in *Proc. 11th Int. IEEE/EMBS Conf. Neural Eng.*, 2023, pp. 1–4.
- [4] M. K. Liu, Y. T. Lin, Z. W. Qiu, C. K. Kuo, and C. K. Wu, "Hand gesture recognition by a MMG-based wearable device," *IEEE Sensors J.*, vol. 20, no. 24, pp. 14703–14712, Dec. 2020.
- [5] O. Sherif, M. M. Bassuoni, and O. Mehrez, "A survey on the state of the art of force myography technique (FMG): Analysis and assessment," *Med. Biol. Eng. Comput.*, vol. 62, no. 5, pp. 1313–1332, 2024.
- [6] H. Fang et al., "Anatomically designed triboelectric wristbands with adaptive accelerated learning for human-machine interfaces," *Adv. Sci.*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 1–14, Feb. 2023.
- [7] E. Nsugbe, "Brain-machine and muscle-machine bio-sensing methods for gesture intent acquisition in upper-limb prosthesis control: A review," *J. Med. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 45, no. 2, pp. 115–128, Feb. 2021.
- [8] Y. Chen, X. Zhang, and C. Lu, "Flexible piezoelectric materials and strain sensors for wearable electronics and artificial intelligence applications," *Chem. Sci.*, vol. 15, no. 40, pp. 16436–16466, 2024.
- [9] L. Guo, Z. Lu, and L. Yao, "Human-machine interaction sensing technology based on hand gesture recognition: A review," *IEEE Trans. Human-Mach. Syst.*, vol. 51, no. 4, pp. 300–309, Aug. 2021.
- [10] W. Dong, L. Xiao, W. Hu, C. Zhu, Y. Huang, and Z. Yin, "Wearable human-machine interface based on PVDF piezoelectric sensor," *Trans. Inst. Meas. Control*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 398–403, Apr. 2017.
- [11] R. Booth and P. Goldsmith, "A wrist-worn piezoelectric sensor array for gesture input," *J. Med. Biol. Eng.*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 284–295, 2018.
- [12] Z. Xiao et al., "Channel selection for gesture recognition using force myography: A universal model for gesture measurement points," *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.*, vol. 32, pp. 2016–2026, 2024.
- [13] A. Radmand, E. Scheme, and K. Englehart, "High-density force myography: A possible alternative for upper-limb prosthetic control," *J. Rehabil. Res. Develop.*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 443–456, 2016.
- [14] M. Zirkel et al., "An all-printed ferroelectric active matrix sensor network based on only five functional materials forming a touchless control interface," *Adv. Mater.*, vol. 23, no. 18, pp. 2069–2074, 2011.
- [15] Y. Abbass, M. Saleh, S. Dosen, and M. Valle, "Embedded electroactile feedback system for hand prostheses using matrix electrode and electronic skin," *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Circuits Syst.*, vol. 15, no. 5, pp. 912–925, Oct. 2021.